

A green approach for the automatic quantitative analysis of additives in plastic samples using in-tube extraction dynamic headspace sampling technique coupled to GC-MS/MS

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HIGHLIGHTS

- First ITEX-DHS method for the quantitative analysis of 47 additives in plastic.
- Applicable to any type of plastic polymer by using a specific calibration.
- Demonstrates good analytical performance with a greenness evaluation score of 0.82.
- Useful for determining additives in microplastics environmental monitoring programs.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Background: Many of the chemicals frequently used as additives have been recognised as hazardous substances, and therefore their analysis is necessary to evaluate plastic contamination risk. Additives analysis in plastic samples is usually performed by methods involving high volumes of toxic solvents or having high detection limits. In this work, a novel, fast, solventless and reliable green method was developed for the automated analysis of plastic additives from plastic samples. The proposed method consists of in-tube extraction dynamic headspace sampling (ITEX-DHS) combined with gas chromatography (GC) and mass spectrometry (MS/MS) determination. **Results:** Several parameters affecting the ITEX-DHS extraction of 47 additives in plastic samples (including phthalates, bisphenols, adipates, citrates, benzophenones, organophosphorus compounds, among others) were optimised. The use of matrix-matched calibration, together with labelled surrogate standards, minimises matrix effects, resulting in recoveries between 70 and 128%, with good quantitation limits (below $0.1 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ for most compounds) and precision ($<20\%$). The method proposed can be applied to any type of polymer, but due to the existence of the matrix effect, calibrates with the adequate matrix should be performed for each polymer.

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Significance: This method represents an effective improvement compared to previous methods because it is fast, solvent-free, fully automated, and provides reliable quantification of additives in plastic samples.

1. Introduction

The exponential increase in the global production and use of plastics has led, in the last decades, to an environmental challenge, not only because of the plastics but also because of the risks caused by the associated chemicals. Plastic materials are organic based polymers that contain chemicals that are either deliberately added (additives) or non-intentionally added substances (NIAS) (side products, breakdown products, and contaminants) [1]. Additives in plastic can be divided into functional additives, (stabilisers, antistatic agents, flame retardants, plasticisers, lubricants, slip agents, curing agents, foaming agents, biocides, etc.); colourants; fillers (mica, talc, kaolin, clay, calcium carbonate, barium sulfate); and reinforcements (glass fibres, carbon fibres) [2, 3]. The concentration of the functional additives in the polymers can vary from 0.001 to 70%, depending on the nature of the additive [2]. Many of the chemicals frequently used as additives have been recognised as hazardous substances, potentially affecting the health of humans and wildlife through e.g. developmental and reproductive toxicity, and, for residual monomers in particular, carcinogenicity and mutagenicity [4]. These additives are found not only in conventional plastic particles but also in bioplastics or biodegradable polymers. As these compounds are usually not chemically bound to the plastic, they can readily migrate to the polymeric surface and leach out into the environment [5]. For all these reasons, the analysis of plastic additives is necessary to evaluate the real risk, for the environment and human health, posed by the presence of plastics in the environment. The European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) characterised over 400 substances used as plastic additives [6]. Some additives like bisphenol A (BPA), Tinuvin 328, Tinuvin 327, and many phthalates have been identified by ECHA as substances of very high concern (SVHC) [7].

This work focuses on the analysis of organic plastic additives in plastic samples, some of which are intentionally added, while others appear in the plastic manufacturing process.

The extraction methods most frequently used for the analysis of additives in plastic (as well as other solid matrices) include dissolution-precipitation [8–10], Soxhlet [10,11], sonication [12–14], microwave-assisted extraction [15–17], or accelerated solvent extraction [18,19]. Nevertheless, all these methods use high amounts of toxic solvents to perform the extraction of additives from polymers. New solventless extraction methods have been proposed in recent years in line with green sample preparation [20]. Among those techniques, headspace extraction [21] and headspace solid-phase microextraction (HS-SPME) [21–23] are equilibrium techniques useful for the analysis of volatile organic compounds but not efficient for less volatile compounds. In recent years, pyrolysis has been applied to the direct analysis of plastic additives. With this technique, the polymer is heated (typically at 600 °C) and the volatilised compounds are directly introduced into the gas chromatograph. Modern pyrolysis systems also allow for the performance of thermal desorption of samples at a lower temperature before the pyrolysis step (dual-shot analysis). The main drawbacks of this technique are the small amount of sample that can be introduced into the caps (a few mg), the difficulties in performing calibration and quantification, and also the damage to the chromatographic system by the direct introduction of dirty/complex samples [24,25].

In-tube extraction dynamic headspace sampling (ITEX-DHS) [26] uses a gastight syringe to pump the sample headspace repeatedly through an attached tube, filled with a sorbent material for analyte enrichment. In this technique, the sample is heated (maximum temperature 200 °C in a Combi PAL autosampler) to facilitate de volatilisation of analytes, and then the headspace is passed through the sorbent

by aspiration with the syringe. Analytes are retained in the sorbent, and once the sorption is finished, they are thermally desorbed in the chromatograph injector. The repeated aspiration of the headspace allows for a more exhaustive extraction of the compounds [27]. Moreover, compared with pyrolysis, ITEX-DHS allows a higher sample size and protects the chromatographic system from dirty samples. For all these advantages (including a solvent-less and fully automated technique), ITEX-DHS coupled with gas chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry seems to be a promising technique for the extraction of analytes with a wide range of volatilities from solid samples, particularly from plastics. Until now, this technique has been used for the analysis of volatile compounds in air [28], hops and beer [29], water [30,31], sea buckthorn [32], apple [33], blood and urine [34], teas [35], honey [36] or alcoholic beverages [37–39], but there are no publications about its use for the analysis of semi-volatile compounds in solid samples.

The main disadvantage of ITEX-DHS compared to other techniques is the complex optimisation of the extraction and desorption conditions. Several factors affect extraction efficiency, such as sorbent selection, incubation temperature, incubation time, number of strokes, trap temperature, desorption temperature, and desorption time. Some of these factors can be interrelated, making the optimisation of the extraction method a challenging task [27,40].

In this work, a new automated method for the quantitative determination of 47 target plastic additives, including phthalates (PAEs), organophosphate flame retardants (OPFRs), and bisphenols (BPs), among others, using the ITEX-DHS sampling technique coupled with GC-MS/MS, was optimised and validated for low-density polyethylene (LDPE). Target additives were selected according to their use, toxicity, and volatility, including some additives recently introduced as less hazardous alternatives (i.e. lawsone, adipates, etc.).

The proposed method was tested for the analysis of other polymers, including a biopolymer, polylactic acid (PLA), and a synthetic biodegradable polymer, adipate terephthalate (PBAT), and then applied to the analysis of polyethylene (PE) and PBAT samples. This is the first study using ITEX-DHS coupled with GC-MS/MS for the quantitative analysis of additives in plastic.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials, reagents and equipment

Extraction was carried out in an automatic sampler platform CombiPAL CTC PAL 3 RTC (CTC Analytics AG, Switzerland) using the ITEX-DHS tool and the incubator. The ITEX-Trap used was Tenax TA 80/100 mesh (Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, USA). The platform is connected to an Agilent 8890 (Agilent Technologies) gas chromatograph, equipped with a multimode injector with a Merlin Microseal™ System to obtain a leak-free seal. The column was an HP-5 MS UI (30 m × 0.25 mm × 0.25 μm). The mass detector used was a triple quadrupole Agilent 7010. Agilent MassHunter 10 was the software used for the analysis and processing of results.

Samples were introduced into 20 mL headspace glass vials from Supelco (Bellefonte, USA).

The eVol™XR handheld automated analytical syringe (SGE Analytical Science, United Kingdom) was used for spiking.

The plastic polymer used for the optimisation was LDPE neat polymer (pristine polymer without any added additives, although the use of some additives is mandatory to perform the polymerisation reactions used in fabrication and processing), in powder form. The average size was 300 μm, the density was 0.918 g cm⁻³ and the melting temperature

Fig. 1. (A) Pareto charts and principal effects graphs obtained from the multivariate optimisation of extraction flow, strokes, and extraction volume. Main effects plot examples (B).

was 105 °C. The microplastic, with the commercial name Lupolen 1800P, was supplied by Lyondell- Basell Industries (Bayreuth, Germany). PBAT resin pellets (Ecoflex 1200) were supplied by AIMPLAS (Spain).

Polypropylene (PP), polylactic acid (PLA), and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) were supplied by Carat GmbH (Germany) as sheet form and cut into 1 cm² squares.

The list of standards and isotopically labelled surrogate standards used, along with their provider, is included in Table 1S of the electronic supplementary material. The working mix solution contains approximately 10 µg mL⁻¹ of each analyte in hexane, except for some phthalate esters (PAEs), which are at a concentration of about 1 µg mL⁻¹ in hexane. The concentration of each analyte in the mix is included in Table 1S of the electronic supplementary material.

2.2. Chemical analysis

For the study, 0.5 g of the microplastic sample was spiked with 25 µL of the working solution in hexane and then left in the laboratory fume hood until the solvent was fully evaporated (about 2 h). Subsequently, the sample was subjected to ITEX-DHS extraction in a 20 mL glass vial. In brief, the sample was initially incubated at 200 °C to transfer the compounds to the headspace. The analytes were then extracted by aspiration (150 strokes) and adsorption in the trap sorbent. Once the extraction is finished, the additives were desorbed at 300 °C in the injection port of the chromatograph (Fig. 1S in the supplementary material). For the validation of the method and analysis of samples, surrogate standards were also added: 100 µL of isotopically labelled standards (Table 1S) (1 µg mL⁻¹ in hexane) and 25 µL of BzB (10 µg mL⁻¹ in hexane).

Most ITEX parameters were optimised in this work, while standard values were selected for other parameters. The trap selected to perform

Table 1

Optimum values of the factors included in the multivariate optimisation. The factors with the asterisk have significant effect on the response.

	Ext flow ($\mu\text{L/s}$)	Strokes	Ext Volume (μL)
TPrP	449	190*	1087*
BHT	449	190*	1100*
Lawson	294	190*	1100*
DEP	449	190*	1096*
BP	449	190*	1100*
Ionox 100	449	188*	1100*
TCPP	449	190	1100
Tinuvin 234	12	190*	1100
Tinuvin 328	128	134	199
BPA	11	156	199
ATBC	449	146	1100*
DEHA	125	132	199
DEHP	114	136	199
DNPP	43	190	199*
Selected	250	150	1000

the experiments was Tenax TA 80/100 mesh, as it is the most widely tested trap and is suitable for a wide range of volatilities and polarities (non-polar to semi-polar volatiles). Syringe temperature was fixed at 95 °C; the trap extraction temperature was set at 40 °C to favour the adsorption of the compounds to the trap (the stability of this temperature was difficult to achieve at lower temperatures). The extraction dispense flow rate was fixed at 100 $\mu\text{L s}^{-1}$, as recommended by the manufacturer. The final conditions of the parameters studied in this work were: 250 $\mu\text{L s}^{-1}$ extraction flow, 150 strokes, 1000 μL extraction volume, 200 °C incubation temperature, 30 min incubation time, 300 $\mu\text{L s}^{-1}$ desorption flow, 300 °C desorption trap temperature, and 1000 μL desorption gas volume.

Gas chromatography conditions were as follows: Injector temperature 320 °C, split mode (split ratio 10:1, with split flow 12.29 mL min^{-1}). The oven program starts at 80 °C (hold 2 min), increasing to 220 °C at 5 °C min^{-1} , and then at 7 °C min^{-1} to 340 °C. Helium was the carrier gas with a constant flow of 1.23 mL min^{-1} .

Regarding the mass spectrometer conditions, the source temperature was 280 °C, at 70eV, and the scan type was dynamic multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) mode. Agilent MassHunter Optimizer software was used to select the transitions for the quantitative and qualitative analysis of each target compound and the collision energy for each transition. Transitions used for each compound and collision energies can be seen in Table 2S of the supplementary material.

2.3. Quantification and quality control

Due to the influence of the matrix in the extraction process, quantitation of the target analytes was performed by matrix-matched calibration (with background subtraction for endogenous polymeric compounds of the polymer used for calibration). Isotopically labelled standards were used as surrogate standards. Calibrations were done by spiking the LDPE neat plastic polymer at a concentration between 0.002 and 10 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ (between 0.0002 and 1 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ for phthalates at low concentration in the working mix (see Table 1S)). Procedural blanks were systematically evaluated by carrying out the ITEX-DHS-GC-MS/MS analysis without sample matrix. These procedural blanks were kept at a minimum by avoiding plastic material as much as possible, using glass material and stainless steel tweezers and spatula to manipulate the samples, and using an eVol™ automated analytical syringe for the spiking to avoid the plastic pipette tips. All the glass material was carefully cleaned (with alkaline soap and rinsed with ultrapure water), and the vials used for the extraction were also calcined and rinsed with methanol before use. A cleaning step of the ITEX trap was included after each samples analysis, consisting of thermal desorption at 340 °C for 2 min under nitrogen flow.

2.4. Statistical analysis

The multivariate optimisation was carried out using Statgraphics Centurion 19.1.2 software. The factors optimised by the multivariate approach were the extraction aspirate flow rate, the number of strokes, and the extraction volume. These factors were introduced in a central composite design 2^3 +star, with 2 centerpoints per block, randomised. The analysis was done in duplicate, resulting in 32 runs (16 × 2). As response variables, 14 target compounds were selected as representatives, including different volatilities and families of compounds (TPrP, BHT, Lawson, DEP, benzophenone, Ionox 100, TCPP, Tinuvin 234, Tinuvin 328, BPA, ATBC, DEHA, DEHP, DNPP). The objective was the optimisation of the response (measured as peak area) of each analyte, taking into consideration also the peak shape. For interpretation of results, principal effect graphs, and estimated response surfaces graphs were used.

3. Results and discussion

To start the optimisation, standard values were assigned to the factors that will be optimised later: Incubation temperature 150 °C, incubation time 30 min, desorption flow 100 $\mu\text{L s}^{-1}$, desorption temperature 340 °C. For other parameters, the value suggested by the manufacturer was selected. Trap temperature was fixed at 40 °C during the adsorption process because a low temperature favours the adsorption of the analytes. This is the lowest temperature that was possible to achieve with stability. In order to simplify the multivariate optimisations, 14 additives were selected (Table 1) as representatives of all the families of compounds and all the range of volatilities. For the univariate optimisations, all the additives were considered.

3.1. Multivariate optimisation: extraction flow, number of strokes, and extraction volume

The first parameters optimised were the extraction flow (the flow of aspiration of the sample through the sorbent), the number of aspiration strokes, and the volume of the sample (headspace) aspirated by each stroke.

The low and high values selected for each optimised factor were 60 and 400 $\mu\text{L s}^{-1}$ respectively for the extraction flow, 30 and 170 strokes, and 300 and 1000 μL for the extraction volume. The optimum values obtained for each one of the representative target compounds can be seen in Table 1. In addition, some examples of the graphs obtained are included in Fig. 1. For most representative compounds, the extraction flow graphs are concave curves (i.e. DEHA or DEP), with an initial increase in signal with the extraction flow, but they decrease with higher values of extraction flow. However, there are some exceptions (i.e. ATBC). As can be seen in the Pareto charts, this factor has no significant effect on the response (for any of the representative analytes), and for this reason, an intermediate value of 250 $\mu\text{L s}^{-1}$ was selected.

The number of strokes performed to retain the compounds in the adsorbent had a significant effect on TPrP, BHT, lawson, DEP, BP, Ionox 100 and Tinuvin 234. As expected, the concentration of the analyte in the ITEX trap is enhanced with the number of strokes, and for this reason, the optimum value obtained for the number of strokes was 190 (DEP as an example in Fig. 1). However, in order to reduce the total analysis time, the number of strokes selected was 150. Regarding the extraction volume, when this factor had a significant effect on the response, the optimum value obtained was about 1000 μL in all cases (e.g., DEP and ATBC in Fig. 1). Additionally, for other compounds like DEHA or DEHP, the optimum was achieved at lower strokes, but for these compounds, this factor did not have a significant effect on the response. Therefore, 1000 μL was selected as the extraction volume.

B: Effect on peak shape

Fig. 2. Optimisation of Incubation temperature. Effect on signal (A), peak shape (B), and plastic integrity (C).

Fig. 3. Effect of the incubation time on the response.

3.2. Univariate optimisation of incubation temperature and incubation time

As a headspace extraction technique, incubation of the sample to facilitate the transfer of the additives to the vial's headspace is necessary. The optimisation of the incubation temperature and time is crucial because these factors are determinants in the amount of analytes in the headspace available for ITEX-DHS extraction. Four incubation temperatures - 50 °C, 100 °C, 150 °C, and 200 °C - were tested. The results obtained for all compounds were quite similar, with low signal at low temperatures and a noticeable increase at 200 °C, as shown in the graphs and images in Fig. 2A for 2,6-DIPN, and triclosan. This result can be explained by the boiling temperature of these additives, which is high (ranging from 110 °C to >400 °C), necessitating a high incubation temperature to facilitate vaporisation. This is the highest incubation temperature allowed by the incubator. For some of the determined additives, the incubation temperature has also influenced the peak shape (e.g. ethoxyquin), resulting in broad peaks at low temperatures and narrow peaks at 200 °C (Fig. 2B). In Fig. 2C, the melting of the LDPE at 150 °C and 200 °C can be observed, promoting the release of the additives. Based on these results, the selected incubation temperature was 200 °C.

For the incubation time, 10, 20, 30 and 40 min were studied. For most compounds, there were small changes with variations in incubation time, lower than 15%. For those compounds that showed significant variations in response with incubation time, in general, there was an increase in response with the incubation time (e.g., TBOEP or DiHP in Fig. 3), but for some compounds (e.g. TCEP or Ionox 100), the response was slightly higher at 30 min than at 40 min. Therefore, the incubation time was set at 30 min.

3.3. Univariate optimisation of desorption flow, desorption temperature, and sample volume

Once the additives are retained in the adsorbent, they must be thermally desorbed in the gas chromatograph injector. To facilitate desorption of the compounds, the ITEX trap is heated, while the syringe

piston moves down (desorption gas volume), pushing the compounds towards the injector. The speed of the piston (desorption flow) and the trap temperature determine the effectiveness of this step and were therefore optimised. Thus, four desorption flows ($100 \mu\text{L s}^{-1}$, $300 \mu\text{L s}^{-1}$, $700 \mu\text{L s}^{-1}$ and $1000 \mu\text{L s}^{-1}$) were tested. This factor has shown low influence for most additives (variation between assays <15%), mainly the most volatile. For those additives more affected by changes in desorption flow (BBP, Chimasorb 81, DEHA, DHNA, DiHP, DINP, DOP, triclosan and Tinuvin 328), the response increases when the desorption flow increases from 100 to $300 \mu\text{L s}^{-1}$ and decreases at higher flows (Fig. 4A, DOP and triclosan as examples). This result agrees with Laaks et al., 2015 [27], confirming that desorption flow is mostly insignificant for volatile compounds, while low volatiles benefit from lower flows. Additionally, peak broadening was observed for the most volatile compounds at low desorption flow; therefore, $300 \mu\text{L s}^{-1}$ was selected as the desorption flow. Two different behaviours were observed when the desorption trap temperature was tested (250 °C, 300 °C, 340 °C). Some compounds showed an increase in signal at temperatures higher than 250 °C, with small differences between 300 °C and 340 °C (e.g. Fig. 4 B, BHT and DMP), but for most compounds, the response was similar at 250 °C and 300 °C and then decreased at 340 °C (e.g. Fig. 4 B, DNPP and triclosan). Therefore, 300 °C was selected. Finally, desorption gas volume was studied. This volume must be high enough to pull down the analytes to the injector, but high volumes can cause the dilution of analytes, and a reduction in their signal. Sample volume was tested between 300 μL and 1300 μL . For most additives (the response of other compounds was not affected by this parameter), the response increases as the desorption gas volume increases (e.g. DEHA and Tinuvin 328 in Fig. 4C) until 1000 μL , decreasing at higher volumes due to the dilution factor. This indicates that 1000 μL was enough to push the compounds to the GC injector, and therefore this volume was selected.

3.4. Validation of the optimised method

Using the optimised conditions (summarised in section 2.2), the method was successfully validated in terms of linearity, trueness,

Fig. 4. Effect of desorption parameters (desorption flow ($\mu\text{L s}^{-1}$), trap desorption temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and desorption gas volume (μL)) on the response.

Table 2

Validation of the analytical parameters. Trueness. Intermediate precision and uncertainty were calculated using pure LDPE spiked the level indicated in Table 3S for each compound (n = 7).

Name	Surrogate Standard	Linearity		Trueness %R±SD	Intermediate precision	M-LOQ	Uncertainty
		Range (µg g ⁻¹)	r ²	(%)	(%)	(µg g ⁻¹)	(%)
Flame retardant							
TPrP	TEP-d ₁₅	0.002–10.1	0.997	109 ± 20	18	0.0011	17
TiBP	BZB	0.002–10.7	0.992	119 ± 11	9.6	0.0003	30
TnBP	TnBP-d ₂₇	0.002–11.5	0.999	118 ± 5.9	5.0	0.0004	24
TCEP	TPhP-d ₁₅	0.004–14.2	0.999	107 ± 21	20	0.0045	21
TCPP	TnBP-d ₂₇	0.002–8.00	0.999	82 ± 8.4	10	0.0660	23
TEEDP	TPhP-d ₁₅	0.003–8.61	0.991	83 ± 7.2	8.7	0.0148	12
TDCPP	TPhP-d ₁₅	0.0034–17.2	0.997	113 ± 7.1	6.3	0.1623	19
TPhP	TPhP-d ₁₅	0.0022–11.1	0.998	111 ± 5.8	5.3	0.0062	16
TBOEP	TPhP-d ₁₅	0.0027–8.23	0.994	109 ± 9.4	8.6	0.0537	9
TEHP	DnOP-d ₄	0.0022–11.2	0.996	112 ± 7.0	6.3	0.0380	18
TPPO	DnOP-d ₄	0.002–6.15	0.996	93 ± 16	17	0.0064	13
TCrP	TPhP-d ₁₅	0.093–11.1	0.996	95 ± 8.9	9.4	0.0048	7
Plasticisers							
DMP	BzB	0.0002–0.80	0.998	98 ± 9.9	10	0.0049	36
DEP	TnBP-d ₂₇	0.049–0.98	0.995	114 ± 11	9.3	0.1603	38
DPrP	TnBP-d ₂₇	0.0002–0.20	0.997	106 ± 7.5	7.1	0.0937	36
DiBP	BzB	0.002–6.49	0.997	117 ± 6.5	5.5	0.0774	24
DnBP	BzB	0.0002–0.599	0.992	88 ± 7.8	8.9	0.2191	36
DMEP	DEHP-d ₄	0.0002–0.79	0.992	88 ± 16	18	0.0199	38
DiPP	TnBP-d ₂₇	0.0002–0.588	0.993	92 ± 9.0	9.7	0.0075	37
NPIP	TEP-d ₁₅	0.0002–0.59	0.992	79 ± 8.9	11	0.0053	38
DNPP	TEP-d ₁₅	0.0002–0.59	0.992	76 ± 4.7	6.2	0.0024	38
DnHP	DEHP-d ₄	0.0002–0.993	0.993	110 ± 9.0	8.1	0.0036	36
BBP	TPhP-d ₁₅	0.0002–0.965	0.995	118 ± 9.1	7.7	0.0227	38
DiHP	DEHP-d ₄	0.0020–9.90	0.996	114 ± 5.3	4.7	0.0020	19
DCHP	TPhP-d ₁₅	0.0002–9.96	0.996	108 ± 3.2	2.9	0.1191	12
DEHP	DEHP-d ₄	0.100–1.00	0.981	123 ± 9.1	7.4	0.0931	37
DOP	DnOP-d ₄	0.0002–0.497	0.995	99 ± 8.2	8.3	0.0002	36
DINP	DEHP-d ₄	0.002–9.92	0.994	107 ± 8.7	8.1	0.0020	16
DIDP	DnOP-d ₄	0.499–9.98	0.997	101 ± 8.1	8.1	0.1000	7
BPA	TPhP-d ₁₅	0.002–10.5	0.992	95 ± 10	11	0.0135	12
BPF	TnBP-d ₂₇	0.99–9.90	0.996	87 ± 12	17	0.1279	30
DEHA	DEHP-d ₄	0.002–5.98	0.996	97 ± 9.9	10	0.0168	8
DTDA	DnOP-d ₄	0.002–10	0.983	96 ± 13	14	0.3250	35
ATBC	TPhP-d ₁₅	0.0019–5.7	0.997	96 ± 15	16	0.0144	13
UV filters							
BP	TEP-d ₁₅	0.002–7.99	0.996	98 ± 8.2	8.3	0.0024	8
Tinuvin 234	DnOP-d ₄	0.499–7.99	0.992	70 ± 12	18	0.0889	15
Tinuvin 327	DEHP-d ₄	0.0020–9.98	0.998	103 ± 15	14	0.0072	12
Tinuvin 328	DEHP-d ₄	0.002–9.97	0.998	99 ± 12	13	0.0072	10
Chimasorb 81	TPhP-d ₁₅	0.99–9.99	0.999	95 ± 8.9	9.4	0.0333	9
Antioxidants							
BHT	DnOP-d ₄	0.002–10	0.992	91 ± 23	26	0.0020	24
TBHQ	TnBP-d ₂₇	3.98–9.97	0.999	112 ± 9.0	10	0.2493	34
Ionox 100	TPhP-d ₁₅	0.002–9.96	0.989	88 ± 21	24	0.3730	30
EQ	DEHP-d ₄	0.002–7.59	0.997	109 ± 15	14	0.0044	14
Antimicrobial							
Triclosan	TPhP-d ₁₅	0.002–6	0.988	116 ± 12	10	0.0101	11
Lawsone	DnOP-d ₄	9.52–30	0.991	128 ± 9.8	10	4.7617	15
Herbicide							
2,6-DIPN	BzB	0.002–9.99	0.998	97 ± 18	19	0.1678	19

Fig. 5. Result of the green assessment, with the colour scale reference, using the AGREE software. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 6. Demonstration of matrix effect by comparison of calibration curves for LDPE and PLA polymers: DMP and TBOP as examples.

precision, and method quantification limits. LDPE neat plastic polymer, spiked with target additive standards at $4 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ level as described in section 2.2., was used for the validation. Tinuvin 770, Irgafos 168 and Irganox 1076 were not validated because they were not properly extracted from LDPE, possibly due to their high boiling point ($>350^\circ\text{C}$), although good results were achieved for other type of polymers, as will be explained in section 3.5. Vitamin E degrades at temperatures higher than 200°C , and therefore the proposed method is not suitable for the quantitative analysis of this compound.

Linearity was evaluated (Table 2) using regression analysis and was expressed by r^2 , obtaining determination coefficients higher than 0.99 in the range indicated in the table. The method quantification limit (M-LOQ) (considering the matrix and the whole procedure) was also calculated. For DMP, BHT, DEP, 2,6-DIPN, TCPP, DiBP, DnBP, DiPP, TDCPP, TEHP, DCHP and DEHP the M-LOQs were determined using the average procedural blank signal (ITEX-DHS-GC-MS/MS analysis without polymer) and 10 times the standard deviation of the blank signal. For the other compounds that were not detected in the procedural blanks, M-LOQs were calculated by a signal-to-noise ratio of 10:1. The M-LOQ obtained were very different depending on the additive, ranging from $0.0002 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ for DOP to $4.8 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ for lawsone (Table 2) due to their different spectrometric response.

Trueness was determined using the analytical recoveries of spiked LDPE samples ($n = 7$) at the level indicated in Table 3S for each compound. The proposed method showed good recoveries (70–128%) for the 47 target additives included in the validation step (Table 2).

The precision of the method was evaluated by determining the intermediate precision as between – day RSD of concentrations over the course of 1 month (7 replicates, concentration level in Table 3S). A good intermediate precision was obtained, with %RSD lower than 20% for all plastic additives, except BHT (26%) and Ionox 100 (24%). The uncertainty (U) of the analytical method was also estimated based on in-house validation data according to the CITAC/EURACHEM guide [41] at the level indicated in Table 3S for each compound. Combined uncertainty (coverage factor $k = 2$, for a 95% of confidence) was calculated as $U = k\sqrt{u_1^2 + u_2^2} + |\mu - \bar{x}|$. The uncertainties associated with the spiked

sample $u_1 = C_{\text{sample}} * \sqrt{\left(\frac{S_{\text{standard}}}{C_{\text{standard}}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{S_{\text{pipette}}}{V_{\text{pipette}}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{S_{\text{flask}}}{V_{\text{flask}}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{S_{\text{balance}}}{m_{\text{standard}}}\right)^2}$, precision ($u_2 = \frac{S_{\text{res}}}{\sqrt{N}}$) and trueness $|\mu - \bar{x}|$ were considered. The relative expanded uncertainty calculated for the whole method was lower than 40% for all the plastic additives (Table 2) (detailed explanation in supplementary material).

The greenness of the optimised method was also calculated using AGREE, the analytical greenness metric approach and software developed by Pena-Pereira et al. [42]. In this software, 12 input variables are transformed into a common scale in a 0–1 range, and the final assessment result is the product of the assessment results for each principle. The overall score is included in the middle of the clock-like graph. The overall score obtained for the ITEX-DHS-GC-MS/MS method was 0.82 (in a range from 0 for the less green, and 1 for the greenness) as can be seen in Fig. 5.

3.5. Suitability of the proposed method for the analysis of other plastics

The method optimised for LDPE was then tested for the analysis of additives from other plastic polymers such as PLA, PET, PP, PHB, and PBAT, although some of them are not included in this work. A different response was observed for some additives, depending on the plastic polymer, indicating the existence of a matrix effect. In Fig. 6, regression curves obtained for DMP and TBOEP (as examples) in a biopolymer (PLA) are compared with those obtained for LDPE. A statistical comparison of both regression curves for both compounds was performed, obtaining a P-values less than 0.01% for the slopes as well as the intercepts, indicating statistical differences among regression curves for both plastics at a 99% confidence interval. This demonstrates the existence of the matrix effect; therefore, this method can be suitable to analyse other types of plastic polymers, but validation (calibration, quantitation limits ...) must be recalculated for each type of plastic, performing new calibrations with the appropriate matrix (spiked neat plastic polymer). The trueness obtained for other polymers is included as an example in table 4S in the supplementary material. Recoveries obtained were quite similar between the different polymers (LDPE, PP, PLA, PET and PBAT) for most of the studied additives, but some

Table 3
Comparison of methods for the analysis of additives from plastic samples.

Extraction method	Compounds	Clean up	Determination	%R (%CV)	Quantitation limits	Reference
ITEX-DHS	PAEs, OPFRs, BPs, benzotriazoles, among others	–	GC-MS/MS	70–128 (2.9–26)	M-LOQ: 2–370 ng g ⁻¹ with matrix	This work
Dissolution-precipitation 100 mL THF+250 mL MeOH	Phenols, amines, and OP antioxidants	–	HPLC-MS	n.a. (2–2.3 %)	LOD: 0.005 mg mL ⁻¹ with standards	[10]
Soxhlet 150 mL DCM, 18 h	PCBs, DDTs, PBDEs, PAHs, NP, BPA	Silica gel column 5 fractions 145 mL solvent mixtures	GC-MS	23–74% (<20%)	n.a.	[48]
Sonication 10 mL H:DCM (1:1), 20 min	Organophosphate esters, adipates, citrates	SPE silica 5 mL elution	UHPSFC-MS/MS	75–124% (<11%)	LOQ: 1–50 ng g ⁻¹ with standards	[14]
MAE 1.8 mL MeOH	PAE, BHT, adipate, cinnamate ...	DLLME	GC-MS	*64–121% (2.38–19.76)	LOQ: 3–195 ng g ⁻¹ with standards	[17]
ASE 30 mL 2.5% cycloH in IPA	Irganox 1010	–	HPLC-UV	94% (0.87%)	n.a.	[19]
Py/TD	PAEs, OPFRs, APs, tinuvin	–	GC-MS	23–100% (0–54)	i-LOQ standards: 5->100 µg mL ⁻¹	[25]
Py/TD	PAEs	–	GC-MS	79–113% (<15%)	n.a.	[43]

UHPSFC-MS/MS: ultra-high performance supercritical fluid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry, H. hexane, DCM: dichloromethane, THF: tetrahydrofuran, MeOH: methanol, EA: ethyl acetate, IPA: isopropyl alcohol, MAE: microwave assisted extraction, DLLME: dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction, ASE: accelerated solvent extraction, BPs: bisphenols, OPFRs: organophosphate flame retardants, APs: alkylphenols, %R: percentage of recovery. n.a.; not available data. * Relative recoveries.

differences between polymers were observed mainly for TBHQ, BPF, Chimasorb 81, Tinuvin 770, DTDA, and Irgafos 168. Good recoveries were obtained for these compounds in some polymers but were not extracted from other polymers. For example, Irgafos 168 cannot be extracted from LDPE and PLA, has poor percentage of recovery from PP (52%), whereas for PET the percentage of recovery was 99%. These corroborates that the interaction of the additives with the polymers is dependent on the polymer type; there is a strong matrix effect for some compounds.

3.6. Comparison with other methods

Few published papers address the quantification of plastic additives; most papers perform the extraction of additives only for qualitative purposes or perform relative quantifications. For this reason, it is difficult to compare the analytical performance characteristics of this method with other approaches. In Table 3, some examples of each technique are included (works that provide the most complete information were selected).

Considering the greenness of the methodologies, only pyrolysis/thermal desorption (Py/TD) is comparable to ITEX-DHS because both are solvent-less fully automatic techniques. The high volume of toxic solvents used in dissolution precipitation, or Soxhlet extraction, accelerated solvent extraction or sonication make these techniques a worse option. In addition, the trueness, precision and quantitation limits of the proposed method are comparable and even better than those obtained with the other methods. The quantitation limits are similar to those obtained with MAE or sonication, but in both cases, they were calculated with standards, and the matrix was not considered. Trueness and precision are also similar that those obtained with sonication or MAE.

Regarding Py/TD, although Akoueson et al. [25] initially considered 56 compounds, they provided analytical performance characteristics only for 10 compounds. Also, the detection limits were calculated using liquid standards placed in the cup without matrix, and the recoveries presented are relative recoveries (first step desorption vs 3 consecutive desorption steps); therefore, the quantitation limits and accuracy reported in this paper are not comparable with those obtained with the ITEX-DHS method proposed. Additionally, good recoveries were reported for the semi-quantitative analysis of PAEs using Py/TD-GC-MS by Kudo et al., in 2019 [43], but those data were obtained at very high concentrations of analytes (1000 µg g⁻¹).

Considering all these factors, the proposed method seems to be a good alternative for the reliable quantitative analysis of additives in plastic samples.

3.7. Analysis of samples

The method was applied for the analysis of two commercial plastic bags, one LDPE bag, and one ecological biodegradable PBAT (polybutylene adipate terephthalate) bag. For the analysis of PBAT bag, calibration was performed on PBAT neat plastic polymer, determining the analytical performance characteristics of the method for this plastic polymer (see Table 4S in the supplementary material). Plastic bags were cut into small pieces of a few mm².

As shown in Fig. 7A and table 5S, the PBAT bag has more plastic additives than the LDPE bag, with plasticisers being the most abundant. However, high concentrations of OFRs and UV filters were also detected. Only for antioxidants, the total content was higher in the LDPE bag than in the PBAT bag, with Ionox100 being the most abundant additive in LDPE, at a concentration of about 8 µg g⁻¹ (Fig. 7B). In the case of the PBAT bag, the main additive was the adipate DTDA (8.5 µg g⁻¹). The presence of more additives in the PBAT bag than in the LDPE bag could be justified by the fact that biodegradable plastic polymers require more chemicals to maintain the desired characteristics in a plastic product [44–46]. The high presence of additives, some of them considered SVHC like DMEP and DCHP, in the biodegradable bag raises questions about this type of materials as a safer alternative to conventional plastic polymers (as additives are more easily released to the environment), unless hazardous additives are replaced by safer compounds [47]. Further studies are necessary to determine the additive composition and environmental risk of these types of polymers.

4. Conclusions

Eight parameters affecting the ITEX-DHS-GC-MS/MS analysis of 47 target plastic additives in plastic samples were successfully optimised using LDPE. The proposed method has demonstrated good quantitation limits (M-LOQ lower than 0.1 µg g⁻¹ for most compounds), trueness (70–128% recovery), and precision (RSD lower than 20% for most compounds). For the reliable quantitation of target analytes, a matrix-matched calibration was applied, considering the influence of the polymeric matrix in the extraction process, using isotopically labelled standards as surrogates. The proposed method for LDPE has demonstrated its applicability to the analysis of other types of plastic (PP, PET, PLA, PBAT), performing a specific calibration for each type of polymer.

The ITEX-DHS-GC-MS/MS method proposed in this work represents an effective improvement compared to previous methods because it is fast, solvent-less, fully automatic, and provides reliable quantification. This method could be useful in monitoring programs for microplastics in

Fig. 7. Results obtained from the analysis of LDPE and PBAT bags grouped by families of plastic additives (A), individual concentrations (µg g⁻¹) (B), and chromatograms (C).

the environment, quality control of plastic products, or leaching studies. The method allows the analysis of additives in a wide range of sample sizes (from microplastics to plastics of a few millimetres) from petroleum-based polymers and bio-based polymers.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Estefanía Concha-Graña: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Carmen M. Moscoso-Pérez:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Verónica Fernández-González:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Data curation. **Purificación López-Mahía:** Validation, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Soledad Muniategui-Lorenzo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2024.342487>.

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